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Techno-economic analysis of power-to-heat-to-power storage for a residential building

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Abstract

Despite the share of renewable energies worldwide is increasing, which can help in reducing the CO₂ emissions, their unpredictability has become a problem due to the mismatch between generation and demand. Among the different alternatives to solve this problem, energy storage is a very interesting solution. Depending on the aim of the storage, there are two types: intra-day or seasonal. The former corresponds normally to a highly efficient and high-cost storage, such as the Li-ion; whilst the latter is a low efficient and low-cost storage. An example of this second type of storage is the power-to-heat-to-power storage, whose efficiency is mainly determined by the heat-to-power converter, and it can be increased if the waste heat produced in the converter is reused in a combined heat and power system.

Given that the residential sector represents a large amount of the global energy use (both electricity and heat), this study has considered a power-to-heat-to-power storage in a fully electrified residential building with a PV installation in order to increase self-consumption and reduce the cost. Both the heating, electricity and cooling demand are supplied by the system.

As this storage technology is currently under an early stage of development, this project aims to understand the main challenges for this storage and the advantages over a very well settled technology, such as the Li-ion. In order to achieve this objective, a model has been created in Matlab. A parametric study has been conducted in which optimum sizing of the components for several scenarios have been considered, as a means to identify the most important parameters that could hinder the feasibility of the power-to-heat-to-power storage system.

From the optimization it was concluded that the scenarios with a thermally driven heat pump for cooling, resulted in larger installations leading to higher cost due to the low coefficient of performance. Regarding the other scenarios which consider an electrical heat pump for cooling, this technology can surpass the Li-ion performance for heat-to-power efficiencies over 20 %. In these cases, the feasibility is clearly hindered by the cost per energy capacity, which must be below 5 €/kWh and could be achieved with silicon; and the cost per power capacity that must be around 300 €/kW. An example of a heat-to-power converter could be the TPV technology which is a solid-state converter, whose efficiency is currently around 30 % and is expected to reduce its cost up to 300 €/kW. In smaller systems, in which the stand-by heat losses have more impact over the system's feasibility due to the larger surface to volume ratio, it is imperative to reduce these heat losses, as well as reduce the cost per energy and power capacities. In addition, it is remarkable that there is no significant improvement when increasing the heat-to-power efficiencies over certain values.

To finish, as this technology increases its feasibility when implemented in large systems, further studies should be done in the industrial and tertiary sector.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CHP	Combined heat and power
COP	Coefficient of performance
DHW	Domestic hot water
DOD	Depth of discharge
P2H	Power-to-heat
H2P	Heat-to-power
HTES	High temperature energy storage
LCOE	Levelized cost of electricity
Li-ion	Lithium-ion
LTES	Low temperature energy storage
Matlab	Matrix laboratory
MTES	Medium temperature energy storage
P2P	Power-to-power
PHPS	Power-to-heat-to-power storage
PV	Photovoltaic
PV _{system}	Photovoltaic systems
PVT	Photovoltaic thermal
RTE	Round trip efficiency
SH	Space heating
STC	Standard test conditions
TPV	Thermo-photovoltaic
UHTES	Ultra-high temperature energy storage

Nomenclature

Symbol	Description	Unit
$E_{\text{left_LT}}$	Energy left stored in the LTES	kWh
$E_{\text{left_MT}}$	Energy left stored in the MTES	kWh
$E_{\text{left_store}}$	Energy left stored in the electrical storage	kWh
$E_{\text{out_LT}}$	Energy out of the LTES	kWh
η_{th}	PVT collector thermal efficiency	%
P_{dem}	Electricity power demand	kW
P_g	PV electricity power generated	kW
$P_{\text{PV_excess}}$	Excess of PV power generation after covering the electricity demand	kW
P_{net}	Difference between the electricity power demand and the PV power generation	kW
Q_{dem}	Demanded heat energy	kWh
Q_{H2P}	Heat energy produced in the H2P converter	kWh
$Q_{\text{left_LT}}$	Heat energy left in the LTES	kWh
$Q_{\text{left_MT}}$	Heat energy left in the MTES	kWh
$Q_{\text{loss_space_LT}}$	Heat energy loss to make space in the LTES	kWh
$Q_{\text{out_LT}}$	Output volume of the LTES	kWh
T_c	PVT collector temperature	°C
$T_{\text{in_colle}}$	Inlet temperature of the PVT collector	°C
T_{LT}	Temperature of the volume stored in the LTES	°C
$T_{\text{out_colle}}$	Outlet temperature of the PVT collector	°C
$T_{\text{out_LT}}$	Temperature of the output volume from the LTES	°C
T_{PVT}	Temperature of the warm volume generated by the PVT	°C
W_{dem}	Electrical energy demand	kWh

1 Introduction

Since 1992 [1] till nowadays, many international agreements have arisen to stop the causes of climate change. One of the most important measures is reducing the CO₂ emissions by increasing the share of renewable energies in the global electricity production up to 50 % by 2030 [2], which currently is mainly covered by hydropower (around 60 % [3]). However, other renewable sources are growing, such as the photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy, which accounted for the 64 % [2] of the yearly 6 % increase of renewable sources installed in the year 2019. This is mainly due to the reduction of costs from 2010 to 2019, 82 % reduction of costs corresponds to the PV installations, and 40 % and 29 % to onshore and offshore wind installations respectively [4]. Despite reaching the CO₂ reduction objective set by the international agreements, when increasing the share of renewable energies, a main problem appears: the generation unpredictability (except for bioenergy) leading to a mismatch between generation and demand. Therefore, among the different solutions proposed to increase their dispatchability, storages play a very important role, not only in giving stability to the grid, but also as a back-up in case of black-out.

There are several types of storages depending on their purpose, however, focusing on the electrical storages used to store excess of electricity generated in renewable energy plants they can be either for large or for small scale installations. At present, the most used storage for large scale installations is the hydro pumped storage, representing more than 99 % of the total capacity installed worldwide [5]. In small scale installations, the alternative to export energy to the grid getting in return a very small profit is to install an energy storage, avoiding oversizing the PV installation and increasing PV self-consumption. Hence, if electrical storages were set-up with a PV installation in the residential sector, which accounted for almost 30 % of the global electricity consumption [6] in 2018, the PV self-consumption would increase. This increase is translated into a reduction in the grid consumption, whose share of renewables represented only 20 % in Europe in 2019 [7], hence, reduction of the CO₂ emissions corresponding to the grid electricity production. Additionally, PV installations for self-consumption help in reducing the electricity losses in the grid and the land exploited by using the roofs of the buildings more efficiently, while at the same time, the consumer's electricity bill is reduced. Providing that the future energy demand is expected to increase, the use of an electrical storage becomes a very interesting solution, and more especially in the residential sector due to the daily mismatch between the PV generation and the demand.

Furthermore, according to a study, self-consumption increases when the system is fully electrified [8]. In this study the capacities of different storages were optimized to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions in Europe installed and when the heating, cooling, electricity and the transport were covered by electricity, the self-consumption increased and a smaller storage capacity is required, showing the importance of electrifying the residential sector.

For this reason, this study will focus on a PV installation with an electrical storage implemented in a completely electrified system in the residential sector. As the storage will be installed with a PV system, it might be logical to think that a short-duration (<10 hours) storage is the most appropriate to fit with the PV fluctuations during the day. However, if a higher level of self-consumption is pursued, longer storages are also required [9]. According to M. Victoria et al. [8], what defines whether the storage is more suitable for long or short term is its efficiency. They concluded that storages with high efficiencies and high costs are more feasible for short-duration purposes, while low-efficient and low-cost storages are more suitable for long-durations. Therefore, to perform for both short and long duration purposes, the high-cost storages' objective is to reduce the costs, while the low cost seek to increase the efficiency.

On the one hand, par excellence, an example of a highly efficient storage is the Li-ion, used in PV installations, but their current high costs and the use of dangerous chemicals difficult to recycle prevent them from being the most sustainable storage.

On the other hand, a low efficient storage that could increase its efficiency is the power-to-heat-to-power storage (PHPS), due to the large heat losses. As a result, if these energy losses were used to warm up a low temperature energy storage (LTES), the overall efficiency could increase [10], and it could be used for both long and short-duration purposes [8].

Figure 1.1 shows a system example with a PHPS, which is contained in the green dashed rectangle. This storage consists of a power-to-heat (P2H) converter, such as a resistive heater or a heat pump, that transforms electricity from an electricity generator, such as a PV system. The generated heat is kept in a high temperature energy storage (HTES) and is transformed into electricity when needed, by a heat-to-power (H2P) converter, such as a turbine or a thermo-photovoltaic (TPV) cell. Given that the H2P converter's efficiency is normally 20 % to 40 % due to the heat losses in the conversion process, the efficiency of the storage is hindered. If this storage were implemented in a CHP or a tri-generation system, where the heat losses in the H2P converter were stored in a LTES, the overall efficiency would increase, as well as the PV self-consumption. Normally the HTES is called ultra-high temperature thermal energy storage (UHTES) due to the high operating temperature ($>1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Figure 1.1. Electricity and heat flow of a PHPS system with a LT storage.

Due to the immaturity of this technology, it would be interesting to do a techno-economic study of the implementation of the PHPS in the residential sector and understand better whose parameters might prevent this system from being feasible.

There has been a previous study [10] related to the feasibility of PHPS as ultra-high temperature thermal energy storage in the residential sector. However, to the best of the author's knowledge, no previous work has been done about installing a PHPS in a completely electrified installation in the residential sector.

This project is related to the European project Nathalie [11], which studies the economic feasibility of implementing the UHTES in commercial, institutional and industrial buildings.

1.1 Aims

The main objective of this project is to analyse the economic feasibility of implementing the PHPS in a fully-electrified installation in the residential sector. As explained before, this technology is in an early stage of development and this study's goal is to analyse which are its challenges. Therefore, a techno-economic analysis is done by comparing the PHPS to a very mature technology in the PV self-consumption sector, such as Li-ion, to have an idea of what are the advantages and disadvantages of this technology.

Given the uncertainty of some of the components' characteristics in this PHPS system, due to the immaturity, this techno-economical study is imperative to understand better what components and parameters have more impact on the system's feasibility. For example, the H2P efficiency and its cost, or cost per power capacity of the PHPS.

In order to do the comparison, a model with the different components is developed, and an optimization of the size them components is made. This optimization is be based on maximizing the economic benefit. The model developed returns the economic viability of the PHPS in different scenarios in order to compare and see under what circumstances the PHPS is feasible.

Hence, various scenarios included in the model, in which a Li-ion or a PHPS are included in a PV installation to supply the electrical, heating, and cooling loads of a fully electrified house, is be performed. The studied system will cover the load requirements of a household located in the city of Madrid. Hence, as residential loads normally use energy during the night hours, the study will assist in determining whether the purpose of the energy storage in a PV system is for only short-term purposes or for both short and long-term.

The different steps and processes followed to successfully fulfil the aims are described in the following section.

1.2 Overall method

In order to meet the objectives of this project, the first thing that has been done is the literature review, to know which studies have already been done related to high temperature thermal storages, as well as define what information will be required during the project. In this first review, it has also been looked at information that could increase the knowledge required to understand the system and the different components.

As shown in the Figure 1.2, after the literature review, the next thing that has been done is understanding the system and its different components, to later implement the system in a model developed in Matrix laboratory (Matlab).

A study of the available commercial components and their characteristics was done, as well as the economic figures that are later used in the optimization and are key aspects when determining the solutions. Depending on the degree of impact over the economic results and the level of uncertainty, some of these data will be considered as assumptions, while others will be studied more thoroughly in a sensitivity analysis.

Once the model was working properly, a database search to obtain data for load profiles was done. Finally, data from a previous study was included, which accounted for SH, DHW, cooling and electricity demand of a household in Madrid. Additionally, the PV generation profile was taken the same study simulated in the software Photovoltaic system (PVsyst) for the selected location and these data will be later scaled by the model to simplify the PV generation in the optimization.

Afterwards, the size of the different components has been optimized for the given load profile and assumptions. To do this optimization, a review of the algorithms available in Matlab has been required in order to select the most appropriate for this particular model.

This optimization was mainly based on minimizing the cost of the energy use, however, other parameters such as the system efficiency or self-consumption will be examined.

Figure 1.2. Flow diagram of the method.

1.3 Previous work

As it has been mentioned in the introduction, including storages in renewable energy installations is very relevant to increase their dispatchability. Additionally, the self-consumption and properly designed storages would release the grid from a large amount of power transfer, hence, no additional infrastructure will be needed and the price of electricity will not increase in excess in the future [12]. On top of that, it must be mentioned that in large systems, storages could participate as grid ancillary services, reducing the payback time of the system investment [9].

This study is focused on PV installations with a storage for self-consumption of a residential load. The most appropriate storage for PV self-consumption installations is, beforehand, the intraday or short-duration storage (e.g. Li-ion), which last around 8 hours [9]. According to P. Albertus et al. [9], who studied how the duration of the storages impacts on the introduction of wind and solar applications, short-duration is imperative to reach a 50 % share of renewables in the role of decarbonisation. However, in order to reach a share over 80 %, both short and long-duration storages (e.g. hydrogen storages), which last over 100 hours, are necessary [9]. Additionally, a study was done [8] in which different storages were installed to reduce the carbonization in Europe for grid connected installations of wind and solar. It was concluded that storages with very high efficiencies and high costs were more appropriate as intraday storages used in solar installations, which is the case of Li-ion batteries. As opposed, low efficient and low-cost storages, such as hydrogen, suit better for long-duration purposes. Hence, in order to find a technology which can work as a short and long-duration storage, there are two possible solutions.

The former is reducing the cost of high-efficiency storages. Par excellence, the chemical batteries are the most used technology due to their high efficiency (normally >70 %) and fast response, and more in particular Li-ion [13]. Li-ion has the largest efficiency, around 90 % [14], largest specific energy, 100-160 Wh/kg [15] and no maintenance is required.

Hence, these characteristics make these batteries very appropriate for electric-vehicles for example, although it also significantly increases their prices. The high costs of an energy storage can be split up in cost per energy capacity (€/kWh) and cost per power capacity (€/kW). In the case of the Li-ion, the high costs correspond to high costs per energy capacity of the materials used, around 320 €/kWh [16] and high cost per power capacity, corresponding to the inverter cost, around 380 €/kW [16]. Despite the decreasing of the cost per energy capacity, the asymptote is expected to have a minimum value of 150 \$ [17], these storages are not always the best solution for PV installations [18], due to their small lifetime, which is around 10 years [19]. It must be mentioned that Li-ion batteries are used for both long and short durations, although currently the feasibility lies below 10 hours of duration [9]. In addition, the chemical storages have the disadvantage of using chemicals, some of which can be pollutant and corrosive.

Another highly efficient storage used for short and long-term [20] is the thermochemical storage, used in CHP systems where rejected heat occurs and can be stored. This storage uses the rejected heat to do reversible chemical reactions, called desorption, in which two components are separated. When the heat is needed, the reaction (adsorption) releases heat. The energy density of this storage is very high [20] which reduces considerably the required space, although the cost is also very high [21]. The main advantage of the thermochemical storage is the zero losses during the storing time as the only heat losses occurs during the charging and discharging [20]. Additionally, the working temperatures are constant and the temperature range is very wide, from 30 °C to almost 1000 °C [21], due to the many different components available. However, this technology is usually used as a LTES (below 100 °C), corresponding to silica gel or zeolite materials [20]. Hence, this storage might not be the best solution to produce electricity due to the low temperatures.

The second solution is to increase the efficiency of a low cost and low efficiency storage. One example of a low efficient storage is the PHPS, which is currently in an early stage of development. The low roundtrip efficiency (RTE) of the system is around 40 % [10], which is mainly on account of the high heat losses in the turbine, used to convert heat into power. However, the overall system efficiency can increase if the heat losses from the HTES and from the turbine are used to heat up a LTES, such as a water tank [10], and use the stored heat for DHW or SH purposes.

PHPS consist of three main components: a HTES that stores the heat transformed by the P2H converter, and the H2P converter that transforms the heat back into electricity. As opposed to chemical storages, the 2 converters in the PHPS systems allow having different input and output power, making it possible to adjust them depending on the requirements of the system. The thermal storage's operation temperature must be very high (over 500 °C) in order to perform as a PHPS. This kind of thermal storages can be divided into 2 types: sensible and latent.

On the one hand, sensible storages keep thermal energy from a temperature difference in a material due to heat transfer, hence depends directly on the thermal capacitance of the material and the rise of temperature. An example of this type of storages are the hot water tanks, which are very interesting due to the high specific energy of the water (~90 Wh/kg from 20 °C to 80 °C) and very low price. However, the maximum temperature is limited by the boiling temperature of the water, preventing it from being used as high temperature storage. Other example could be rocks, as their melting temperature is much higher, but the main problem is the container damage due to the volume expansion of the rocks with high temperatures.

On the other hand, the latent type stores energy through a change in the state in the material, depending on the latent heat of the material and the phase change temperature, which is why this material is also called phase change material (PCM). The main advantage of the latent storage is the constant output temperature, which is very important to obtain constant

output power in the H2P converter. The temperature of the change of phase must be high enough and its thermal conductivity and thermal stability at the operation temperatures are also required for the storage material.

Some materials used in latent storages are silicon, whose melting temperature is 1400 °C and its latent heat is around 1200 kWh/m³ [22], or boron which melts at around 2100 °C and has a latent heat of 2600 kWh/m³. The large energy density of boron makes it a very interesting material, but its price is very high compared to silicon. Hence, an alternative option is silicon and boron alloys, which melt at a lower temperature than silicon, but their energy density is larger than 1000 kWh/m³. When working at such high temperatures (>1000 °C), these storages are called UHTES. Other common latent thermal storages are the molten salts used in concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, whose melting point temperatures and energy density are far lower than the ones mentioned before.

Some utility scale examples of latent high temperature storages are shown in the reference [23]. The storage with largest temperature corresponds to the project by the company 1414 Degrees in Australia which is planning on building a 400 MW PV plant with silicon thermal storage [24]. The other examples have lower operation temperature, which mainly correspond to molten salt storages. Current existing installations and research development are focusing on the implementation of latent heat storages as PHPS, not only for utility scale, but also for smaller systems [10], [17], [22]–[24].

One of the advantages of the PHPS is the low energy specific cost of the storage, which is mainly due to the low cost of the materials. As mentioned before, most of the existing PHPS are made of silicon due to its low price (1.6 \$/kg [17]) and its wide availability in the world, among other reasons, which makes the cost per energy capacity of the storage very low. However, what impacts on the cost per energy capacity of the PHPS is its insulation (30 % of the energy cost of the storage [17]) since the operation temperature is very high. Another component that increases the overall cost of the PHPS is H2P converter cost per power capacity. In a study in which grid storages were analysed to know the profitability of selling electricity when the price was high, and buying it at low price [9], it was concluded that a high cost per power capacity can be balanced with a low cost per energy capacity of the storage [9].

Despite the high theoretical efficiency of H2P converters at 1200 °C, around 80 %, options are thermo-photovoltaic (TPV) cells, which potential cost per power capacity of the TPV technology goes around 300 €/kW [25]. TPV cells can work at very high temperatures with a refrigeration system and transforms into electricity the radiation of an emitter in direct contact to the high temperature material. The bandgap is properly designed to the long-wave radiation of the emitter. Some tested examples are the GaAs or InGaAs, which cost more than silicon cells [17]. However, the power density reached is also larger [17] due to its efficiency above 30 % at temperatures over 1300 °C [26]. In addition to the lack of moving parts, TPV cells have the advantage of responding much faster than turbines, making them a more attractive solution to PHPS systems [17].

Given the low efficiency of the H2P converter, it is a large source of heat losses in the H2P and entails a very large cost in the whole PHPS investment, it might seem reasonable to study these parameters in the project. A. Datas et al. [10] concluded that in PHPS systems in the residential sector, where the heat losses were used for supplying heating loads, improving the insulation and the efficiency of the turbine do not give the best economic results. This is because the rise in the overall cost do not balance out the energy gains [10]. Therefore, a compromise between the insulation quality and the efficiency of the H2P converter must be reached.

Another improvement to the system could be replacing the standard PV modules by PVT modules, in which the heat from the PV module is removed and transferred to a fluid,

increasing the efficiency of the module while storing the heat from the fluid in the LT thermal storage.

1.4 Key figures

A proper selection of the key figures has a great importance to compare different scenarios which is the case of this study with an electrified system. Hence it could be intuitive that the LCOE would be the most ideal figure as it considers the cost of the whole installation per electricity unit demanded.

However, in this case there are some scenarios which have different electricity demand for the same need due to the use of either a THP or an EHP. Therefore, a specific cost of the energy (SCE) demanded could be a better solution to compare the cost of the whole installation normalized to the total energy. This is defined in the:

$$SCE = \frac{CAPEX + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{OPEX(t)}{(1 + WACC_{nom})^t}}{E_{dem}} \quad \text{Equation 1.1}$$

In the equation above, the SCE depends on the $CAPEX$ (€), defined as per Equation 1.2, and the $OPEX$ (€/year), shown in Equation 1.3; divided by the sum of the total yearly energy demanded, E_{dem} (kWh/year), calculated through the Equation 1.4.

$$\begin{aligned} CAPEX = & C_{e-el-store} W_{el-store} + C_{p-ch} P_{inmax-el-store} \\ & + C_{p-disch} P_{outmax-el-store} + C_{p-pv} P_{nom-pv} \\ & + C_{e-LTES} Q_{LTES} + C_{p-chiller} P_{max-cool} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 1.2}$$

Where the $CAPEX$ (€) depends on the cost of the electrical storage itself, $C_{e-el-store}$ (€/kWh), the P2H converter cost, C_{p-ch} (€/kW), the H2P converter, $C_{p-disch}$ (€/kW) and C_{e-LTES} (€/kWh) which are the electrical storage cost per energy capacity, the charging and discharging power converters cost per power capacity, and the LTES cost per energy capacity, applying the components' sizes: $E_{el-store}$, $P_{inmax-el-store}$ (kW), $P_{outmax-el-store}$ (kW) and E_{LTES} (kWh), respectively. Moreover, it depends on the nominal PV power installed, P_{nom-pv} (kW) and the cooling maximum capacity of the chiller, $P_{max-cool}$ (kW), multiplied by their respective cost per power capacity, C_{p-pv} and $C_{p-chiller}$ (€/kW).

$$\begin{aligned} OPEX = & W_{grid} C_{var-grid} + P_{max-grid} C_{fix-grid} \\ & - W_{exp-grid} C_{exp-var-grid} + P_{nom-pv} C_{maintenance} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 1.3}$$

The equation above shows that the $OPEX$ corresponds to the energy bought from the grid, E_{grid} (kWh), the maximum power allowed by the contracted electricity, $P_{max-grid}$ (kW), minus the electricity exported to the grid, $W_{exp-grid}$ (kWh), multiplied by their respective specific cost, variable for the energy bought, $C_{var-grid}$ (€/kWh) and $C_{exp-var-grid}$ (€/kWh), and fixed $C_{fix-grid}$ (€/kW) for the power contracted. In addition, the maintenance cost is included dependent on its cost per power capacity, $C_{maintenance}$ (€/kW) and the nominal PV power installed, P_{nom-pv} (kW).

$$E_{dem} = E_{electr} + E_{heat} + E_{cool} \quad \text{Equation 1.4}$$

Finally, the total energy demanded, E_{dem_total} (kWh) is the sum of the energy for power, heating, and cooling demand (kWh), E_{electr} , E_{heat} , E_{cool} respectively.

Other relevant key figures are the efficiency of the system and the self-consumption (SC) shown in the Equation 1.5 and Equation 1.6 respectively.

$$\eta_{system} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_{dem}(t) + Q_{dem}(t) \eta_{P2H}}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_{in_PV}(t) + W_{grid}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 1.5}$$

The efficiency of the system, $\eta_{system}(\%)$, represents how large the energy losses in the system are, whose value on the output energy towards the system (kWh) each hour (t) of the year, corresponding to the electricity and heating demand, W_{dem} and Q_{dem} applying a P2H efficiency η_{P2H} ; with respect to the total input energy towards the system (kWh): W_{in_PV} and W_{grid} , which are the PV input electricity plus the total grid consumption.

$$SC = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_{in_PV}}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} W_{PV}} \quad \text{Equation 1.6}$$

The equation above defines the SC as the total input electricity generated by the PV installation with respect to the total PV electricity generated, showing how much PV electricity has not been used on the site of the system.

It is worth noticing that all these calculations will be done for one year as all the inputs and outputs are considered constant during the lifetime of the system. Only the economic calculations will take into account the installation lifetime.

2 System description

2.1 Boundary conditions

2.1.1. Site and PV generation

This study will simulate different scenarios for a residential building located in Madrid, in the centre of Spain. The specific location of the house is at latitude 40.37° N and longitude 3.8° E.

Table 2.1. Site boundary conditions.

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Value</i>
Latitude, Longitude	40.37°, -3.8°
Average max. temperature	32 °C [27]
Average min. temperature	3 °C [27]
Yearly irradiation	1.6 MWh/ m ²

For this location, it was simulated in a previous study, a PV installation with a nominal peak power of 1 kW and the optimum tilt in the software PVsyst. The irradiation, ambient temperature and other weather data were obtained from the Meteonorm database available in PVsyst.

Electrical losses in the PV installation have been considered when simulating its power generation, whose data will be later used to scale up the installation capacity. However, it must be mentioned that after scaling, no additional losses, specially from having different connections and shading losses, have been taken into account.

Table 2.2. PV installation characteristics.

<i>Installation characteristics</i>	<i>Value</i>
Nominal peak power	1 kW
Tilt angle	36° (optimum) [28]
PV generation	1400 kWh/kW/year

In order to simplify and reduce the computational time, PV degradation has not been considered in the model.

2.1.2. Load analysis

The load profile has been acquired from a previous study in which a simulation [10], performed in the software EnergyPlus, obtained the electricity, heating and cooling demand on an hourly basis.

The four loads will be grouped into two: heat (SH and DHW) and electricity, and the cooling can be included in either of the two groups depending on the chiller used.

Despite being a fully electrified system, the two different loads will be distinguished during the simulations as the heating load is covered by a water tank and the demand from the tank will differ from one scenario to another.

The different assumptions for the characteristics of the building and other relevant data used in the EnergyPlus simulation are listed in the Table 2.3 below.

The DHW and the electrical daily load profiles are defined constant during the year, whilst the heating and cooling demand are dependent on the weather of the site.

The SH and the cooling start when the indoor temperature reaches a setpoint. The SH setpoint temperature is equally distributed during the winter months: 17 °C in October to 20 °C in January, and the cooling setpoint is fixed to: 25 °C in June, to 27 °C in September.

In the Appendix A, more detailed figures are presented for the DHW, SH, cooling and electrical demand.

Table 2.3. Building characteristics used in the simulation software EnergyPlus.

<i>Data</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Units</i>
Floor area	60	m ²
Nb of floors	2	-
Percentage of glazing	30	%
U-value walls	0.26	W/(m ² ·K)
U-value roof	0.18	W/(m ² ·K)
SH setpoint temp. (Jan/Oct)	20/17	°C
DHW inlet/outlet temp.	15/60	°C
Cooling setpoint temp. (June/Sept)	25/27	°C
Lighting power density	5	W/ m ²

Once again, the load has been assumed to be constant every year to simplify and safe computational resources. The yearly data can be observed in the Table 2.4.

Table 2.4. Yearly energy demand.

<i>Type of energy</i>	<i>Yearly value</i>
SH (thermal energy)	14.2 MWh
DHW (thermal energy)	1.4 MWh
Electricity energy	2.8 MWh
Cooling energy	4.6 MWh

2.1.3. Economic assumptions

The main selection criteria to compare the different cases is the economic results which are defined by the SCE, shown before in the Equation 1.1. Hence, the selection of the economic assumptions is critical.

In the Table 2.5, the different economic assumptions considered in the model are shown. The impact of these parameters over the feasibility of the system might be studied in a sensitivity analysis and will be presented in the discussion section.

It has been assumed that there are no economic benefits from selling the PV surplus to the grid.

Table 2.5. Economic assumptions used in the LCOE calculation.

<i>Component</i>	<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Value</i>
PV installation (incl. additional inverter after half of the lifetime of the installation)	C_{p-pv}	PV: 1100 €/kW [29] PVT: 2100 €/kW [30]
Li-ion	$C_{e-el-store}$ $C_{p-disch}$ C_{p-ch}	Today: 323 €/kWh [16] Future: 150 €/kWh [8] 380 €/ kW [16] -
PHPS	$C_{e-el-store}$ $C_{p-disch}$ (electrical) C_{p-ch} (electrical)	30 €/kWh [10] 1000 €/ kW [31] 100 €/ kW [32]
Hot water tank	C_{e-LTES}	30 €/ kWh [10]
Absorption chiller (THP)	$C_{p-chiller}$ (cooling)	500 €/kW [10]
Electrical chiller (EHP)	$C_{p-chiller}$ (cooling)	500 €/kW [10]
Economic data	$C_{var-grid}$ $C_{fix-grid}$ $C_{var-grid-exported}$ $WACC_{nom}$ inf_{el} Economic lifetime	0.17 €/kWh [10] 50 €/kW [10] 0.00 €/kWh 4 % [16] (PV self-cons) 2 % [10] 25 years

2.2 Model description

The model created in Matlab simulates the performance of a completely electrified installation of a residential home, supplying all the energy demands. The inputs of the model are the heating and cooling power demand, whose values will vary depending on the location, and the electrical demand. The model simulates the whole performance of the system for a year with time steps of one hour. This yearly data is used in a calculation with an economic lifetime of 25 years.

In order to meet the household load, two electrical sources will be included in the system: a PVT installation and the grid. When the PVT electricity generation is not enough to cover the load, the grid will act as a backup. An electrical storage will be included in the model as a backup to increase the PV self-consumption and reduce the demand from the grid.

In the Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2, the scheme with the PHPS and the Li-ion battery is shown. All in all, there is a PVT installation supplying heat and electricity, an electrical storage storing the PV excess generation and providing electricity (and heat in the case of PHPS) to cover the load. There is also a LTES which stores the heat generated in the PVT and in the H2P generator, as well as a MTES storing water at a larger temperature (~ 80 °C) with a P2H generator, which is an electrical resistance.

Figure 2.1. Example of the PHPS with the inputs and outputs to the components.

Figure 2.2. Example of the PHPS with the inputs and outputs to the components.

2.2.1. System control

The model simulates the performance of the whole system with hourly resolution (Δt) for a year and at the beginning of the simulation, all the storages are assumed to be empty. In each of the time steps of the simulation period, it is verified separately in the model whether there is electric (W_{dem}) or heat demand (Q_{dem}), despite being an electrified system.

The decision making of the model is shown in detail in the Appendix B and Appendix C, which is explained in the following steps below. All the steps are common to both electrical storages models with some differences which will be explained.

1. PV electricity evaluation in the PHPS & Li-ion

The main criteria considered in the model is to prioritize covering the electrical load (P_{dem}) with the PV generation (P_g) when possible.

On the one side, if there is more PV generation than electric demand, it will be evaluated in the step 5 which will be the use criteria with the excess of generation, P_{PV_excess} .

On the other side, if P_{dem} is larger than the P_g , it will be first evaluated whether the electrical storage can meet the excess of demand without risking the safety of the

storage, going beyond the depth of discharge (DOD), assumed to be 100 % for simplicity. In the case of the PHPS, the discharging has some heat losses associated represented by heat at a constant temperature (Q_{H2P}) which will be an input to the LTES. In case of the energy stored in the storages not being enough, the grid will supply the required amount of electricity.

2. PVT heat generation evaluation in the LTES

In parallel with the previous step, the output temperature of the PVT (T_{PVT}) is compared to the temperature (T_{LT}) of the energy stored in the LTES (Q_{left_LT}).

If T_{PVT} is larger, the model will give priority to the higher temperature energy from the PVT (Q_{PVT}) storing in the LTES as much energy, taking in mind the LTES maximum energy capacity. This means that if the LTES is a charged (with a lower temperature), the model will discharge as much energy from Q_{left_LT} , if more space is needed, and store all the Q_{PVT} . These heat discharging losses are considered in the energy balance of the LTES and in the system.

If on the contrary, T_{PVT} is smaller, it will be prioritized introducing the PVT energy and increasing Q_{left_LT} despite T_{LT} will be reduced. In this case, if the LTES is full, the model will dismiss this Q_{PVT} and will be considered as heat losses.

3. H2P losses evaluation in the LTES

In the same way as in the previous step, the output temperature of the H2P converter losses (T_{H2P}) is compared to the LTES temperature (T_{LT}) and the same criteria will be followed.

4. Update the LTES output energy to cover the heat demand

In this step, it is checked how much energy is required to be heated by the P2H converter in the MTES to increase the temperature of the LTES up to setpoint temperature of the MTES.

5. Heat demand evaluation in the MTES, PHPS or Li-ion, and LTES

In this step it is evaluated whether the required electrical power from the grid, from the PV or from the Li-ion, and the heat from the PHPS will supply the heat to warm up the output volume from the LTES. It must be kept in mind that P_{PV_excess} from the step 1 will prioritize covering this heat demand (Q_{dem}) over the charging of the electrical storage.

It is first checked whether Q_{dem} can be supplied by the energy stored in the MTES (Q_{left_MT}).

If it is possible, the charging of the electrical storage (PHPS or Li-ion) with P_{PV_excess} will be prioritized over charging the MTES. Finally, if there is still more P_{PV_excess} , the MTES will be charged.

If on the contrary, the heat stored in the MTES is not enough to cover the Q_{dem} , P_{PV_excess} will be used to cover as much as possible Q_{dem} . When it is not enough, it will be first checked whether the electricity stored in the Li-ion can cover it, and if not, the grid will supply the rest. In the case of the PHPS, the heat will be directly supplied by the heat stored, rather than converting the stored heat into electricity and then back into heat.

6. Return cooling return to the LTES (case of THP)

As the temperature of the return volume from the THP at 70 °C is always larger or equal to T_{LT} , all the cooling energy is introduced in the LTES. Again, it will be prioritized storing the warmer water and there will be discharging heat losses if space is needed.

7. Update the energy left and the temperature for the following time-step
 In this step the self-discharging losses are applied to the thermal storages. Both the PHPS and the MTES have losses in the energy stored, whilst the heat losses in the LTES are represented as temperature reduction, as explained in the chapters 2.3.1 and 2.3.2. The Li-ion storage has no self-discharging losses.

In order to check the accuracy of the model, an energy balance of the whole system has been done for the whole year, considering the inputs outputs and losses in the system. This is shown in the Equation 2.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{tot \text{ balance system}} &= E_{tot \text{ in system}} - E_{tot \text{ out system}} - E_{tot \text{ loss system}} \quad \text{Equation 2.1} \\
 &- E_{left_{store}}(8760) - E_{left_{MT}}(8760) \\
 &- E_{left_{LT}}(8760)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where the total system energy balance (kWh), $E_{tot \text{ balance system}}$, is the total sum of inputs in the system during a year (kWh). $E_{tot \text{ in system}}$, minus the total outputs (kWh), $E_{tot \text{ out system}}$, and the energy losses (kWh), $E_{tot \text{ loss system}}$; minus the energy left at the last time-step of the year in the electrical storage, the MTES and the LTES (kWh): $E_{left_{store}}(8760)$, $E_{left_{MT}}(8760)$ and $E_{left_{LT}}(8760)$, respectively.

2.3 Components model

2.3.1. Electrical storage

The model of the electrical storage has one input which corresponds to excess of PV which is stored with a certain charging efficiency (η_c), and the output is used to cover the electrical and heating demand and will vary depending on the type of electrical storage. The two electrical storages modelled, and later compared, are the Li-ion and the PHPS.

The storage component is divided into two main parts: the storage itself and the converters. The former is related to the amount of energy that can be stored and has a specific cost depending on the energy capacity. The latter corresponds to the H2P, H2P and the power-to-power (P2P) converters, that depends on the amount of maximum input/output power to the storage, and their specific cost depend on the power.

Figure 2.3 shows the scheme of the Li-ion, where the input and the outputs to are put into the same converter. The charging and discharging efficiencies are assumed to be equal and are calculated based on the round-trip efficiency of the Tesla Powerwall [19]. The stand-by losses are neglected in the model due to the low losses of the Tesla Powerwall [19].

Figure 2.3. Scheme of the charging and discharging of the Li-ion.

In order to check the model, an energy balance Li-ion storage was calculated as per Equation 2.2, integrating the input and output power in each time step.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{balance\ Li-ion} &= -\Delta W_{int\ Li-Ion} + W_{in-store} - W_{out-store} \\
&\quad - E_{Li-ion\ loss}
\end{aligned}
\tag{Equation 2.2}$$

Where the $E_{balance\ Li-ion}$ is equal to the difference between the input electricity from the PV excess (kWh), $W_{in-store}$, and, the internal energy change of the Li-ion (kWh), $\Delta W_{int\ Li-Ion}$, the output energy to cover electricity and heat (kWh), $W_{out-store}$, and the charging and discharging losses of the Li-ion, $E_{Li-ion\ loss}$, which are dependent on the input/output power and the roundtrip efficiency. The result of the energy balance will be checked for each of the results given in the following sections.

The PHPS scheme is shown in the Figure 2.4. The input corresponds to the input to the store ($P_{in-store}$), which is transformed into heat in a P2H converter, and stored in the PHPS with ideal charging efficiency (η_c) of 1 as it is a heat resistance. The storage can supply, on the one hand, electricity demand ($P_{out-store}$) with a certain constant discharging efficiency (η_d), and losses ($1-\eta_d$) are in form of heat at low temperature (Q_{H2P}). While the PHPS discharging efficiency has a great importance in this study as it is a large source of heat losses and large cost associated. Hence, the discharging efficiency and cost of the H2P will be studied in a sensitivity analysis.

The heating demand at higher temperature than the heat losses will be covered directly by the stored heat (Q_{PHPS}) with the heat discharging efficiency ($\eta_{d_HT_heat}$) assumed to be 1.

Figure 2.4. Scheme of the charging and discharging of the PHPS.

Providing that the PHPS is a latent HT storage, the heat is stored in the phase change and the temperature of the whole storage is constant. Hence, the stand-by losses of the PHPS (Q_{loss_HT}) correspond to heat losses which are modelled as constant heat losses which will depend on the temperature difference with the ambient air, the volume of the storage and the quality of the insulation cover.

The heat losses to the ambient are defined as per the Equation 2.3:

$$Q_{loss\ HT} = UA \Delta T = UA (T_{PHPS} - T_{amb})
\tag{Equation 2.3}$$

Where the losses depend directly on the heat loss coefficient, UA (W/°C) and the temperature difference (ΔT). The temperature difference is calculated between the surface the phase change temperature (T_{HT}) of the material stored and the ambient temperature (T_{amb}), assumed to be 25 °C. These losses are constant due to the constant temperature in all the storage while the material is still on the phase change, which is assumed to be the only way of storing the energy in the PHPS. This means that once the storage is completely in solid state, the heat losses are not considered, and the storage is assumed to be fully discharged.

Given that the model is thought to optimise the energy capacity (and volume) of the storages, and in order to avoid defining the radius and height separately to model different storage capacities, the equation used in the EN 12977-3 to define the UA value of a tank has been finally used. This norm validated the heat loss of storages from a series of hot water tanks with the same characteristics, with volumes within 200 to 600 l.

$$UA = a_{PHPS} \sqrt{V_{max\ PHPS}} \quad \text{Equation 2.4}$$

Where the UA value depends directly on the square root of the volume of the store ($V_{max\ PHPS}$) in m^3 and the a_{PHPS} ($W \cdot m^{3/2} / ^\circ C$) coefficient, which is an unknown value for the PHPS technology and will also be studied in a sensitivity analysis.

It must be mentioned that this norm is not accurate for this specific storage, however, given that the a_{HT} coefficient is an unknown value for this technology, if a relation between the height and the radius of the cylinder is set, the real U_{cover} could be calculated as a reference.

The $V_{max\ PHPS}$ is calculated from Equation 2.5:

$$V_{max\ PHPS} = \frac{E_{max\ PHPS}}{E_{dens\ PHPS}} \quad \text{Equation 2.5}$$

Where the volume depends on the maximum energy capacity of the PHPS (kWh), $E_{max\ PHPS}$, storage and the energy density of the material stored (kWh/l), $E_{dens\ PHPS}$.

The energy density corresponds to the latent energy, calculated as per Equation 2.6.

$$E_{dens\ PHPS} = 6.74 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot T_{PHPS}^2 - 1.72 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot T_{PHPS} + 0.14 \quad \text{Equation 2.6}$$

Where the $E_{dens\ PHPS}$ (kWh/l) of a material is the given phase change temperature T_{PHPS} [10].

The charging and discharging of energy only take into account the material latent energy. Once the material is completely melted, the storage is considered to be charged whilst when it is solidified, it is discharged. Hence, given the constant temperature assumed in all the volume, the heat losses are modelled as constant and there are no heat losses once the storage is completely discharged. In the model, the energy losses are removed from the left energy stored at the end of each time step. Hence the energy balance of the PHPS is calculated as shown in the Equation 2.7:

$$E_{balance\ PHPS} = -\Delta Q_{intPHPS} + Q_{in-store} - Q_{out-store} - Q_{loss\ PHPS} \quad \text{Equation 2.7}$$

Where the $E_{balance\ PHPS}$ is equal to the difference between the input energy from the PV excess (kWh), $Q_{in-store}$, and, the internal energy change of the PHPS (kWh), $\Delta Q_{intPHPS}$, the output energy to cover electricity and heat (kWh), $Q_{out-store}$, and the standby heat losses of the PHPS during that time step (kWh), $Q_{loss\ PHPS}$.

2.3.2. Cooling

The cooling demand is covered either by an electric heat pump (EHP) or a thermal heat pump (THP) depending on the scenario. If an EHP is used, the cooling load is supplied by electricity and it is determined by its electrical coefficient of performance (COP_e).

If as opposed, a thermal heat pump (THP) is installed, the temperature of the LT storage, which will be used to feed the THP, must be higher (around 80 °C) than the temperature in the previous case. The amount of heat demanded is defined by its thermal COP_{th} . In this case, the outlet temperature of the chiller is stored in a LTES at its return cooling temperature.

2.3.1. LTES

This storage is modelled as a stratified tank with two levels, a warm and a cold one. In the Figure 2.5, the inputs and outputs of the LTES are shown. The upper part stores the heat at a low temperature coming either from a PVT system (Q_{PVT}) with varying temperature, from the H2P converter heat losses (Q_{H2P}) at a constant temperature, or from the return flow of the THP (Q_{cool}) used for cooling (if applicable), also set at constant temperature. The cold part is set to constant temperature which is an average of the tap water temperature and the SH return temperature, which is also equal to the ambient temperature (25 °C) for simplification. Hence, the temperature of the whole tank is set to 25 °C when it is completely empty.

Figure 2.5. Scheme of the charging and discharging of the LT storage.

Given that the stored heat has a varying temperature depending on the source, the LTES is modeled by a warm left volume and a temperature. When there is input heat, the updated T_{LT} is the weighted average of the temperature of the volume stored in the tank before storing the heat, whilst the input volume is the sum of those volumes. As mentioned in the control system in the section 2.2.1, if space is required to store some input volume, there will be some heat losses called $Q_{loss_space_LT}$.

When there is heat demand, either for SH, DHW or cooling (if THP is applicable) and the energy stored in the MTES is not enough to supply it, a P2H converter warms up the required volume to fulfil the demand. This volume is taken from the top of the LTES and can be either warm at T_{LT} if the LTES is charged, or cold if discharged. Thus, the output of the LTES corresponds to the volume required by the MTES in order to supply all the volume demanded and the left warm volume in the LTES is updated accordingly. In order to simplify the whole model, the charging and discharging efficiencies ($\eta_{c_LT_heat}$ and $\eta_{d_LT_heat}$) are assumed '1'.

Given that the temperature of the LTES is variable, the heat losses are calculated as a reduction of the warm water temperature, calculated as per Equation 2.8 below:

$$T_{LT} = \frac{E_{leftLT} - E_{lossLTES}}{C_{pwater} \rho_{water} V_{leftLT}} + T_{inLT} \quad \text{Equation 2.8}$$

Where the updated temperature after applying the losses, T_{LT} (°C), depends on the difference between the energy left in the store before the losses and the heat losses, E_{leftLT} and $E_{lossLTES}$ (kWh) respectively, the specific cost coefficient of the water at 60 °C, C_{pwater} (kW/(°C·kg)), the density of water at that temperature, ρ_{water} (kg/l), the store volume of water in the LTES, V_{leftLT} (l), and the ambient temperature, T_{inLT} (°C). The $E_{lossLTES}$ are calculated by using the Equation 2.3 and Equation 2.9, substituting the heat losses coefficient by a_{LT} and the LTES temperature T_{LT} , whose value varies in time.

In order to check the fidelity of the model, an energy balance is calculated as shown in the Equation 2.10:

$$E_{balance\ LTES} = -\Delta Q_{intLTES} + Q_{PVT} + Q_{cool} + Q_{H2P} - E_{loss\ space} - Q_{out_LT} - E_{loss\ LTES} \quad \text{Equation 2.10}$$

In the equation above, the $E_{balance\ LTES}$ is equal to the sum of the input energy from the PVT (kWh), Q_{PVT} , the return flow of the THP (kWh), Q_{cool} , and the heat losses in the H2P converter (kWh), Q_{H2P} , minus the internal energy change of the LTES (kWh), $\Delta Q_{intLTES}$, the output energy to the MTES (kWh), Q_{out_LT} , the energy losses to make space in the LTES (kWh), $E_{loss\ space}$, and the standby heat losses of the LTES during that time step (kWh), $E_{loss\ LTES}$.

2.3.2. MTES

This storage is a thermal sensible storage, modelled as a hot water tank which stores heat at a constant temperature T_{MT} by a P2H converter. This constant temperature depends on whether the cooling is supplied by an EHP or a THP. In the Figure 2.6, the inputs and outputs to the MTES are shown. The reason why the MTES is modelled with a constant temperature compared to the LTES is because the former is heated up by an electric heater, while the latter has several inputs with different temperatures.

Figure 2.6. Scheme of the charging and discharging of the MT storage.

The MTES is modelled so that the output water from the LTES (Q_{out_LT}) is put into the MTES after applying some electrical power from the PV, the grid, and the Li-ion storage (if applicable), or directly supplying heat power from the PHPS (if applicable). The output of the MTES model is the heating demand (Q_{dem}) set at a constant temperature of T_{MT} . As both,

charging and discharging, efficiencies are assumed to be ideal ($\eta_{c-MT-elect}$, $\eta_{d-MT-heat}$, $\eta_{c-LT-heat}$), the only losses considered in the model are the stand-by losses ($Q_{loss-MT}$).

The charging of the MTES only occurs when there is still excess of PV generation after checking whether it can be stored in the electrical storage. If there is still PV excess, the charging occurs with volume from the LTES after being warmed up to the T_{MT} by the excess of power. Hence, the amount of volume depends not only on the excess of PV, but also on the temperature of the LTES and is defined as per Equation 2.11.

$$V_{stored_MT} = \frac{W_{excess-PV}}{C_{pwater} \rho_{water} (T_{MT} - T_{LT})} \quad \text{Equation 2.11}$$

Where the stored heated volume depends on the input energy $W_{excess-PV}$ (kWh), the specific heat coefficient of the water, C_{pwater} (kWh/(kg·K)), the density of the water, ρ_{water} (kg/L), and the increase of the temperature. The increase of temperature is the difference between the inlet temperature (T_{in-LT}) defined to be 25 °C, and the setpoint temperature ($T_{setpoint-LT}$), which is considered constant depending on the simulated cases, which will be explained in the following section.

As the model assumes the charging and discharging of the storage at constant T_{MT} , the stand-by losses are simulated as a reduction of the stored volume, rather than in reducing the temperature.

$$V_{left-MT}(t) = V_{left-MT}(t-1) - \frac{Q_{loss-MT}}{C_{pwater} \rho_{water} (T_{MT} - T_{amb})} \quad \text{Equation 2.12}$$

Where the volume left in the MTES at the beginning of the time-step, $V_{left-MT}(t)$ (l), is calculated from the volume left at the end of the previous time-step, $V_{left-MT}(t-1)$ (kWh), minus the energy heat losses, $Q_{loss-MT}$ (kWh), divided by the specific heat coefficient of water at 80 °C C_{pwater} (kW/(°C·kg)), the energy density of water at that temperature, ρ_{water} (kg/l), and the difference between the temperature of the MTES and the ambient temperature, T_{MT} and T_{amb} (°C) respectively.

The heat losses ($Q_{loss-MT}$) are modelled similarly to the PHPS given its constant temperature, but depending on its SOC, using the Equation 2.3 and Equation 2.13 and substituting the heat losses coefficient by a_{MT} , setpoint temperature of the MTES, T_{MT} and the volume left stored (l), $V_{left-MT}(t-1)$. In the same way as in the PHPS, the energy losses are removed at the end of each time step, after all the input and output heat have been applied to the model.

Again, an energy balance was calculated as shown in the Equation 2.14 and Equation 2.10 for the MTES and the LTES, respectively.

$$E_{balance\ MTES} = -\Delta Q_{intMTES} + Q_{PV-MT} + Q_{PHPS} + Q_{grid-MT} + Q_{Li-Ion-MT} - Q_{dem} - Q_{loss\ MT} \quad \text{Equation 2.14}$$

In the equation above, the $E_{balance\ MTES}$ is equal to the difference between the input energy from the PV excess (kWh), Q_{PV-MT} , and, the internal energy change of the MTES (kWh), $\Delta Q_{intMTES}$, the output energy to cover the heat demand (kWh), Q_{dem} , and the standby heat losses of the MTES during that time step (kWh), $E_{loss\ MT}$.

2.3.3. PVT model

The PVT model has been done for a single collector which produces both heat and electricity. The heat will be stored directly on the LTES when possible, while the electricity produced by the PV module can be stored either in the PHPS or in the MTES, depending on the conditions. The inputs and outputs of the model can be seen in the Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7. Inputs and outputs to the PVT module.

The system has been modelled in such a way that each hour, the temperature in the bottom of the LTES is pumped through a collector with a constant flow rate, and the outlet temperature of the fluid is calculated depending on the collector temperature (T_c), the thermal efficiency of the collector (η_{th}), the incidence irradiance on the plane and the ambient temperature. The collector temperature and the efficiency are calculated each time step through an iterative process till the T_c converges following the Equation 2.15

$$T_c = \frac{(T_{out\ collec} + T_{in\ collec})}{2} \quad \text{Equation 2.15}$$

Which shows that the collector temperature, T_c , is an average of the inlet and outlet collector temperatures, $T_{in\ collec}$ and $T_{out\ collec}$. The outlet temperature of the collector was previously calculated from the Equation 2.16.

$$T_{o\ collec} = T_{in\ collec} + \frac{G_{inc} A \eta_{th}}{\dot{V} C_{pwater} \rho_{water}} \quad \text{Equation 2.16}$$

The equation above shows that the outlet collector temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), $T_{o\ collec}$, depends on the inlet temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), $T_{in\ collec}$; the incidence irradiance on the collector (kW/m^2), G_{inc} ; its area (m^2), A ; the thermal efficiency (%), η_{th} ; and the flowrate (l/h), \dot{V} , and the thermal capacity of the water ($\text{kWh}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$), C_{pwater} . Its thermal efficiency is calculated from Equation 2.17.

$$\eta_{th} = \eta_o - a_1 \cdot T^* - a_2 G_{inc} T^{*2} \quad \text{Equation 2.17}$$

Where the collector thermal efficiency (%), η_{th} , depends on the optical efficiency (%), η_o ; the heat losses coefficients $a_1(\text{K}^{-1})$ and $a_2(\text{m}^2/(\text{K}^2\cdot\text{kW}))$; the incident irradiance (kW/m^2), G_{inc} , and the mean reduced temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), T^* , which is calculated as per Equation 2.18:

$$T^* = \frac{(T_c - T_{amb})}{G_{inc}} \quad \text{Equation 2.18}$$

Which depends on the collector temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), T_c , calculated in the previous iteration; the ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), T_{amb} , and the incident irradiance (kW/m^2), G_{inc} . Both, the incident global irradiance and ambient temperature data were taken from the Meteornorm database available in PVsyst, the same data as used for the PV generation.

When T_c converges, $T_{o\ collec}$ is compared with an objective temperature and if it is lower, a feedback process starts in which $T_{o\ collec}$ is fed back into the collector as $T_{in\ collec}$ in order

to increase the outlet temperature up to the objective temperature. Each feedback, this evaluation is performed and only if the objective temperature or a maximum number of feedbacks are reached, the process ends. The maximum number of feedbacks each hour depends on the minimum volume of the circuit, which will be considered the volume of one collector.

This feedback process lasts an hour independently on the number of feedbacks, and when it ends, $T_{o\ collector}$ is compared with the objective temperature. If it is lower, the heated volume is not stored as it has not reached the desired temperature, and the next time step starts with a new iteration and fresh cold water from the bottom of the tank.

Hence, the heat produced by the PVT every hour will be calculated by

$$Q_{PVT} = V_{useful} \rho_{water} C_{pwater} (T_{o\ collec} - T_{bottom-tank}) \quad \text{Equation 2.19}$$

Being Q_{PVT} (kWh) the heat produced by the PVT collector directly dependent on the volume that has reached the objective temperature (l), V_{useful} defined in the Equation 2.20; the density of the water (kg/l), the water specific heat capacity (kWh/(kg·K)), C_{pwater} ; and the temperature difference between the outlet collector temperature (°C), $T_{o\ collec}$, and the temperature at the bottom of the tank (°C), $T_{bottom-tank}$.

$$V_{useful} = \frac{1\ h}{n_{feedback}} \dot{V} \quad \text{Equation 2.20}$$

The equation above shows that the useful volume (l), V_{useful} , depends on the number of feedbacks each hour, $n_{feedback}$, and the flow rate (l/h), \dot{V} .

The useful volume and its temperature for one single collector is used to later calculate the heat production scaling up the PVT installation size to meet up the required nominal power.

The AC electrical power generated by the PVT installation is calculated as per Equation 2.21:

$$P_{PV} = \eta_{el} G_{inc} A (1 - \eta_{loss}) \quad \text{Equation 2.21}$$

In the equation above, the hourly electrical power generated by the PVT collector (W), P_{PV} , is calculated by the electrical efficiency (%) of the PV module, η_{el} defined in the Equation 2.22; the incidence irradiance (kW/m²), G_{inc} , and the area of the collector (m²), A . The PV production is hindered by some losses (%), η_{loss} , associated to the shadowing, electrical losses, etc., which have been assumed constant in order to simplify the model and its value is 14 %.

$$\eta_{el} = \eta_{el,o} \beta_{Pmpp} (T_c - T_{o\ STC}) \quad \text{Equation 2.22}$$

Where the electrical efficiency of the PVT collector (%), η_{el} , is directly dependent on the reference electrical efficiency (%), $\eta_{el,o}$; the power temperature coefficient (%/°C), β_{Pmpp} , and the temperature difference between the collector temperature and the reference temperature at standard test conditions (STC) (°C), $T_{o\ STC}$.

In the same way as in the heat generated, the electrical power of one module will be scaled up to meet the nominal power of the total installation, applying some losses (14 %) in order to consider the shading, the components losses, etc.

The heat and electricity generation for a 1 kW installation is shown in Table 2.7 below:

Table 2.6. PVT installation characteristics.

<i>Installation characteristics</i>	<i>Value</i>
Nominal peak power	1 kW
Tilt angle	36° (optimum) [28]
Electricity generation	1470 kWh/kW/year
Heat generation	5000 kWh/kW/year

2.4 Technical assumptions

In Table 2.7 below, the different assumptions used to run the simulations are shown.

Table 2.7. Technical assumptions used in the model.

Component	Characteristic	Value
PV installation	P_{nom-PV} (kW)	Optimized
PVT installation	P_{nom-PV} (kW) T_{PVT}	Optimized 40 °C (setpoint)
Li-ion	$E_{el-store}$ (kWh)	Optimized
	$P_{inmax-el-store}$ (kW)	Optimized
	$P_{outmax-el-store}$ (kW)	$P_{inmax-el-store}$
	Self-discharging losses	0 %
	RTE	90 %
	DOD	100 %
PHPS	$E_{el-store}$ (kWh)	Optimized
	$P_{inmax-el-store}$ (kW)	Optimized
	$P_{outmax-el-store}$ (kW)	Optimized
	T_{PHPS}	1200 °C
	$E_{density}$	1 kWh/l
	Thermal losses	$0.1 \text{ W}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3/2}$
	DOD	100 %
Hot water tanks	E_{MTES} (kWh)	Optimized
	E_{LTES} (kWh)	Optimized
	Thermal losses	$0.1 \text{ W}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3/2}$
	P2H converter efficiency	100 % (heat resistance)
	T_{MTES}	80 °C (for THP) 60 °C (for EHP)
Thermally driven heat pump (THP)	COP_{th}	0.7
	$T_{in_chiller}$	$T_{MTES} = 80 \text{ °C}$
	$T_{out_chiller}$	70 °C
Electrical heat pump (EHP)	COP_{el}	4
Others	T_{amb}	25 °C

2.5 Optimization process

Once the model has been developed in Matlab, an optimization algorithm must be selected. This kind of algorithm is implemented by selecting which parameters of a function are to be optimized and will minimize a certain merit function.

The selected merit function is the SCE defined as per Equation 1.1., which will be minimized by varying the parameters listed below:

- Maximum capacity of the electrical storage (E_{el_store})
- Nominal power of the PV installation (P_{nom_PV})
- Maximum output power of the electrical storage ($P_{outmax_el_store}$)
- Maximum input power of the electrical storage (only applicable to the PHPS) ($P_{inmax_el_store}$)
- Maximum capacity of the LTES (E_{LTES})
- Maximum capacity of the MTES (E_{MTES})

$P_{inmax_el_store}$ is set to $P_{outmax_el_store}$ in the case of the Li-ion battery as the maximum output power is equal to the maximum input power.

Therefore, this optimization is a 6-dimension (or 5-dimension for the Li-ion) problem whose function to be optimized is non-linear. Among the different algorithms available in Matlab used for this kind of problem, the genetic algorithm, the pattern search and the Nelder and Mead simplex method were studied for being the most appropriate [33], [34].

These three methods are stochastic, which means that all the solutions found will be different. Therefore, the algorithms are run several times in order to reach a global minimum of the function.

After several tests carried out, it was concluded that the algorithm which led to better results was the simplex method. This algorithm is implemented in a function created by John D'Errico [35].

The designed algorithm selected a couple of random initial points which are the inputs of the simplex function. After getting the same number of optimized points as the number of defined initial points, the best one is selected as the input of the simplex function with some variations in order to get a more accurate optimum. The best point out of these last simulations is selected as the optimum value.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Base case

The tri-generation fully electrified system has been simulated in six different scenarios shown in Table 3.1. Three of them have assumed a standard PV installation and the other three have a PVT one. All the scenarios have an electrical storage; in the case of the Li-ion battery, the cooling is supplied by an EHP, whilst the scenarios with PHPS installed, simulate both the THP and the EHP.

Table 3.1. Definition of the six scenarios studied.

PV installation			PVT installation		
PHPS		Li-ion	PHPS		Li-ion
EHP	THP	EHP	EHP	THP	EHP
Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6

These simulations have been performed as a base case with the technical and economic data presented in the tables presented in the sections 0 and 2.4 mentioned before, varying the H2P efficiency of the four PHPS scenarios. The range of the efficiencies simulated go from 10 %, up to the Carnot efficiency at 1200 °C, 80 %. In the case of the Li-ion, the two scenarios have been carried out with a constant efficiency and the present cost both mentioned in the previous sections.

The optimum sizes of the components in the first three scenarios (with PV) are shown in Figure 3.1, and the last three (with PVT) are shown in Figure 3.2. From these figures it can be observed that the scenarios with the THP (black line) have a larger PV installation and electrical storage capacity, leading not only to a higher capital investment, but also to an unreasonable solution of PV size for a residential house due to the limiting roof space. Regardless the THP can make use of the heat from the LTES for cooling, more electrical power is needed in order to warm up to a higher temperature to run the THP, compared to the EHP. In addition, such large storage capacities in the THP scenarios show that these installations require a long-term electrical storage in order to be feasible, but compared to the installations with EHP, the cost is larger. The high capital investment and operational costs of the THP are reflected in the SCE in Figure 3.3. It must be mentioned that the MTES size for the THP has some fluctuations which might be due to the optimization algorithm finding local minimums, rather than a global one. These variations are also reflected in the SCE of the THP.

From Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4, it can be seen that the SCE is lower for the scenarios with EHP. Focusing now on these more profitable scenarios, the PHPS becomes feasible at efficiencies over 50 % in the case of the scenario 1, whilst in the scenario 4, the H2P efficiency must be above 70 %, showing that for low efficiencies the system would rather storing the heat produced by the PVT (scenario 4) and the electricity in the MTES than installing a PHPS. As it could be expected, when the PHPS is not feasible (its optimum size is 0 kWh), the LTES capacity is 0 kWh, as well as in the scenario 3 with the Li-ion. On the other side, in the scenarios 4 and 6, the LTES has values different than 0 kWh due to the PVT heat production.

Figure 3.1. Components' sizes of the PV installation scenarios.

Figure 3.2. Components' sizes of the PVT installation scenarios.

It can be noted how, even with almost a double specific cost of the PVT compared to the standard PV installation; the overall SCE is smaller for the scenarios 4 and 6. The high PVT cost is translated into a smaller and more reasonable PV installation size. This reduction of the PV installation size might be due to the low temperature heat production, which is likely to be one of the main focus in this electrified installation due to the large proportion of heating load compared to electrical. Hence, having a source of heat at low temperature benefits this system, despite the apparent high cost of the PVT. Thus, having the chance of increasing the heating generation with the PVT installation, significantly increases the profitability of the installation compared to a standard PV. However, it is very interesting to

see that, despite increasing the H2P efficiency, in the scenarios 1 and 4, the SCE decreases slightly.

Figure 3.3. SCE for the PV installation.

Figure 3.4. SCE for the PVT installation.

3.2 Parametric study of the stand-by heat losses in the PHPS and its specific cost

From the previous simulations, the scenarios 2 and 4 have been dismissed for not being economically feasible, whilst the scenarios 4 and 6 have been removed due to the reduced available time and space, however it could be interesting to do the same parametric study for those scenarios. Thus, from this section, the study will be focused only on the scenarios 1 and 3. The former corresponds to a PHPS system, and the latter to a Li-ion battery, both with an EHP for cooling and a PV installation.

Given that the main source of losses in the PHPS is the stand-by heat loss to the ambient, a parametric study will be done from an ideal PHPS without heat losses and very low cost per energy capacity ($C_{e-el-store}$), till the base case shown in the section 3.1, which is a more realistic scenario, with heat losses and a reasonable cost per energy capacity. This cost includes the cost of the material stored, the case and the insulation layers, so the better the insulation, the more expensive the cost per energy capacity is. Therefore, four scenarios with a PHPS with varying H2P efficiency, shown in

Table 3.2, have been simulated and compared to the current and future cost per energy capacity of the Li-ion for a fixed efficiency. The ideal PHPS scenario (Scenario 1) will determine the theoretical limit of the PHPS for this proposed system.

Additionally, in order to see the impact of the cost per power capacity of the H2P converter (C_{p_disch}), which is another important parameter for this technology, an optimistic and a pessimistic scenario have been simulated. These values correspond to the cost per power capacity of a TPV cell, which can achieve efficiencies over 40 % with a relatively low cost, ($< 500 \text{ €/kW}$) [31]. Hence the optimistic has been set to 300 €/kW whilst the pessimistic is assumed 1000 €/kW (taking as a reference the PV installation cost)

Table 3.2. Assumptions for the 8 different scenarios.

Scenario		$C_{e\text{-el-store}}$ (€/kWh)	Heat loss coefficient ($W \cdot K^{-1} \cdot dm^{-3/2}$)	C_{p_disch} (€/kW)
Scenario 1.	A	5	0	300
	B	5	0	1000
Scenario 2.	A	5	0.1	300
	B	5	0.1	1000
Scenario 3.	A	30	0	300
	B	30	0	1000
Scenario 4.	A	30	0.1	300
	B	30	0.1	1000

In Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6, the results from the optimization of the scenarios with the optimistic and pessimistic cost of the H2P converter respectively, are shown. It can be seen how the sizes of the components in the scenarios 2 and 4 (with heat losses, line pink) tend to the same values as the Li-ion when increasing the H2P efficiency. This means that despite the different economic costs, when both storages have the same efficiency, the optimum sizes for this system are also the same. However, due to the stand-by losses of the PHPS compared to the Li-ion, the SCE is significantly larger in the pessimistic scenarios. Additionally, it must be noticed that it is not profitable to install a PHPS unless reaching a H2P efficiency of 30 % and 50 % for the realistic scenarios 4 A and B respectively. The lack of an electrical storage for lower efficiencies is translated into a reduction of the PV power installed for these scenarios, as well as a 0 kWh LTES and a larger MTES, as it could be expected.

The optimum storage capacity for the scenario 1 is far larger than the rest of the scenarios. However, the maximum output power of the storage does not increase accordingly as it could be expected, showing that for a scenario with no heat losses and low energy cost, the PHPS would perform as a long duration storage, for having a high energy capacity and low maximum output power. The power to energy ratio for the rest of the scenarios are kept to a lower value, as for the Li-ion case, meaning that both storages in those cases are used for short-duration purposes.

Despite the electrical storage capacity diminishes when increasing the H2P efficiency and the PV power installed is kept at a constant level, the maximum input power is reduced, and so the PV self-consumption. However, as it will be seen in the following section, for the scenario 4, the self-consumption increases due to the constant size of the MTES when the PV installed is constant and the PHPS capacity decreases.

Regarding the maximum output power, it is kept at a constant level when varying the H2P efficiency, depending on the scenario. In the case of the high H2P converter cost, the output power for the worse scenarios (2 and 4) is 0.8 kW. When checking the electrical power demand in the Appendix A, whose daily profile is constant during the year, the peak power in the night corresponds to this same power. This shows that the electrical storage for short-duration purposes must be at least the peak power when there is no PV production, aka at night.

Figure 3.5. Components' sizes with an optimistic cost of the H2P converter.

Figure 3.6. Components' sizes with a pessimistic cost of the H2P converter.

3.3 Parametric study of the stand-by heat losses in the PHPS and its specific cost when scaling up the load

As concluded from the previous simulations, the heat losses are one of the main focus for the PHPS to reach economic feasibility. Hence, given that stand-by heat losses are directly dependent on the area of the PHPS container, whilst the energy capacity depends on the volume stored, it is logical to think that when increasing the size of the PHPS, the heat losses compared to the amount of energy stored are reduced, as the area to volume ratio is reduced. Moreover, the specific cost of peak PV power installed is reduced, which is likely to happen

when increasing the load. For these reasons, the same parametric study as in the section 3.2, has been performed for two scaling factors, as shown in the Table 3.3. In these simulations, the cost per power capacity of the PV installation has been reduced to 900 €/kW for being a larger installation.

Table 3.3. Assumptions for the 4 different scenarios scaling up the load.

Scenario		$C_{e-el-store}$ (€/kWh)	Heat loss coefficient ($W \cdot K^{-1} \cdot dm^{-3/2}$)	C_{p_disch} (€/kW)	C_{p-PV} (€/kW)	Scaling factor
Scenario 1.	A	5	0	300	900	x 100
	B	5	0	1000		
Scenario 2.	A	5	0.1	300		
	B	5	0.1	1000		
Scenario 3.	A	30	0	300		
	B	30	0	1000		
Scenario 4.	A	30	0.1	300		
	B	30	0.1	1000		

In Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6, the results from the 8 scenarios mentioned before are shown.

Figure 3.7. Components' sizes when scaling up the load and having an optimistic cost of the H2P converter.

Figure 3.8. Components' sizes when scaling up the load and having a pessimistic cost of the H2P converter.

Now it can be noticed how the scenarios 1 and 2 (low cost per energy capacity), and 3 and 4 (high cost per energy capacity) are very similar for H2P efficiencies above 20%. In this case, the former scenarios have installed PHPS for long-duration purposes, whilst the latter aims to be an intra-day storage, as well as the Li-ion.

Again, the PV size for efficiencies over 20-30% is remained constant although in this case the MTES increases when decreasing the storage capacity. In the case of the scenario 1 without heat losses nor cost of the storage, the PV installation is 1 MW smaller than the scenario 2 with losses. Meaning that a large amount of the PV generation is lost in form of heat losses.

3.4 Discussions

In the figures below, the key figures of the two parametric studies performed are shown, comparing the results from the different scenarios.

Figure 3.9 shows the SCE and it can be seen that the PHPS in small systems (first column of graphs), in the scenarios 2 and 4 (with heat losses, pink lines) cannot even reach today's Li-ion cost until 80% efficiency for the optimistic H2P cost. Whilst in the scenarios 1 and 3 (without losses, blue lines), the PHPS can boost the future's Li-ion cost for efficiencies over 40% with both optimistic and pessimistic cost of the H2P converter. Hence, even if the cost of the H2P converter is low, as per the optimistic scenario, the PHPS cannot surpass the Li-ion cost if the heat losses are not reduced. Contrary to what happens in small systems, in large systems (second column of graphs), it can be clearly seen that for the scenarios 1 and 2 (with low cost per energy capacity, circle marker), the PHPS is a better option than the Li-ion at H2P efficiencies over 20% for the optimistic H2P cost.

Therefore, when the cost per energy capacity and the H2P cost are larger, the PHPS is not likely to reach the future's Li-ion cost. Again, the H2P cost plays an important role in determining the profitability of the PHPS over the Li-ion, although in this case, the other important parameter is the cost per energy capacity of the storage.

Figure 3.9. SCE of the parametric studies for small (first column) and large systems (second column) against the efficiency for an optimistic and pessimistic specific cost of H2P converter.

In addition, it is very interesting to see that in all the scenarios, the SCE does not improve much when increasing the efficiency of the H2P converter over 30-40 %. For smaller values, SCE decreases with increasing H2P efficiency, due to the reduction of the PV power installed, the capacity of the electrical storages and the maximum input power.

It must be mentioned that, despite the ranges of the efficiencies simulated go from 10 %, up to 80 %, which is the Carnot efficiency at 1200 °C, reaching high H2P efficiencies might not be feasible. This is due to the very large capital cost when increasing the efficiency, thus the current maximum efficiency of the different H2P converters is 45 % [36]. In the case of the gas turbines with an efficiency of 35 %, its cost is more than 800 €/kW [37], [38] for large scale installations, although for smaller scales, the cost can be very high, up to 10000 €/kW [16]. On the other side, the TPV efficiency is 40 % [31] at cost per power capacity of 1000 €/kW with a potential cost of 300 €/kW. Hence, reaching efficiencies over 40 % of a H2P converter is not possible and the PHPS cannot surpass the Li-ion battery in the realistic scenarios of the small-scale load.

Another important point from the figures is the smaller difference between the scenarios 3 and 4, and 1 and 2, for larger systems than for smaller ones. This detachment from the stand-by heat losses can be appreciated in the SCE graph, in which the scenarios 1 and 2, corresponding to the low cost per energy capacity of the storage (circle marker), have better results than the 3 and 4 (triangle marker), despite the 2 and 4 have heat losses (pink lines). Therefore, when analysing a larger system, it can be concluded that the cost per energy capacity hinders more the profitability independently of the heat losses.

To have a better reference of the heat losses assumed in these cases, Table 3.4 shows the UA-values corresponding to the storage capacity of a solution from the small and large-scale scenarios. In order to give a better idea, the UA-value for a LTES has been also calculated.

Table 3.4. UA-value for three different volumes and energy densities.

Energy capacity (kWh)	Energy density (kWh/l)	Volume (l)	UA-Value (W/K)
20	1 (silicon alloy)	20	0.45
2000	1 (silicon alloy)	2000	4.5
60	0.04 (water $\Delta T=35$ °C)	1400	3.8

When looking at the self-consumption and the efficiency in Figure 3.10 and Figure 3.11 from the parametric study of scaled-up load, it can be clearly seen the tendency towards the Li-ion's values when increasing the H2P efficiency in all the scenarios. There is a reduction of the PV self-consumption with the increasing H2P efficiency for the same PV installation size, which seems to be related to the reduction of the maximum input power of the PHPS providing the constant PV power installed and the storage capacity.

The scenario 2 shows a slightly smaller efficiency due to the higher heat losses of the PHPS, whose size is the same as in the scenario 1 without heat losses. The system efficiency graph shows how the PHPS stand-by heat losses in a scaled-up system has less weight in the overall losses with respect to the energy stored. Hence, self-consumption in the Li-ion, and also in the PHPS when increasing the H2P efficiency, is not only limited to its maximum capacity, but also to the maximum input power.

Despite PV self-consumption being larger with lower efficiencies, it is translated into lower system efficiencies meaning that the heat losses produced in the H2P converter are not utilized in the system. This shows that this key figure is just a way of defining how well the PV installation has been designed, but together with the losses, a new key figure could be defined. Due to the difficulty in determining which losses corresponded to the grid and which to the rest of the installation, this key figure was not considered and a mixture between the overall system efficiency and the PV self-consumption was finally used.

Figure 3.10. PV self-consumption of the parametric studies for small (first column) and large systems (second column) against the efficiency for an optimistic and pessimistic specific cost of H2P converter.

Figure 3.11. System efficiency of the parametric studies for small (first column) and large systems (second column) against the efficiency for an optimistic and pessimistic specific cost of H2P converter.

Regarding the possibility of varying the P_{outmax} and P_{inmax} ratio in the PHPS, it is clearly an advantage over the Li-ion as it can be adjusted depending on the demand, size, and daily profile, as well as on the PV generation. In the Figure 3.12, the variations of this ratio are shown depending on the H2P efficiency and how this flexibility enables detaching the PV production from the demand side in this installation. It can be clearly seen how in the scenarios with low cost per energy capacity, the input power significantly higher than in the other cases (for a maximum output power not changing too much in comparison). This means that for a constant PV size, when the cost of the storage is very low, it is more profitable to make the storage a bit larger, rather than storing the PV excess in the MTES.

Figure 3.12. P_{out}/P_{in} ratio of the PHPS for the results in the parametric study.

It has been observed from the results that given the mismatch between the PV generation and the energy demand, an energy storage is needed. As it was expected the Li-ion battery has been proved to be used as an intra-day battery in the system due to the low energy capacity to power output ratio. In the case of the PHPS, it could be concluded from the literature that, given the low cost and the low efficiency, it was rather used for long-duration purposes than for short-durations. However, in the EHP scenarios, the PHPS had very similar results as the Li-ion, even with low efficiencies, which might be due to the increase of the system efficiency by reusing the heat waste in the H2P converter.

When the PV installation sizes increased, the optimum size of the energy storage also increased, either the electrical or the MTES. This was clearly seen in the case of the THP scenarios in which the PV installation was very large, and the electrical storage was used for long-duration purposes. When the THP was used, the heating load during the summer is severely increased due to the low COP, compared to the load during the winter. This shows that the PHPS can be used either for long or for short duration purposes as there are optimum solutions of both types. However, it must be mentioned that the assumption of not losing energy once the PHPS is completely solidified and in order to say a statement like this, a more accurate model of losses should be done.

3.5 Uncertainties

From the results shown in the sections above, it can be seen how the heat losses and the cost per energy capacity of the storage can significantly hinder the profitability of the PHPS when comparing it to the Li-ion. Moreover, the H2P efficiency is also a parameter that prevents the PHPS from being feasible under certain values, in some cases even under 50. However, when increasing the efficiency of the H2P converter, its cost per power capacity is likely to increase as well, which has been seen from the previous results seen that can impact on the feasibility of the PHPS. Hence a trade-off between the efficiency of the H2P converter and its cost is highly important. As well as reaching a balance between the stand-by heat losses and the cost per energy capacity of the storage, which includes the insulation cost. When increasing the scale of the storage, it has been observed that the stand-by heat losses have less importance than the cost per energy capacity, showing an opportunity of reducing the cost per energy capacity without risking the feasibility if the insulation quality is reduced.

It can be seen how the model is a tool that can achieve interesting results just by inputting electricity and heating demand with hourly resolutions, despite the uncertainties. Hence this tool will be of interest in future works to simulated different scenarios than the ones mentioned in this project.

However, it must be mentioned that all the conclusions from the results reached by the model are based on the assumption that the optimization algorithm finds the minimum global point. However, it must be mentioned that the algorithm is limited due to the wide range of possible solutions and the restricted available computing time, as seen in the results section, some results look a bit unusual. In addition, the algorithm bases the optimization on a defined key figure, hence a proper selection is crucial in determining the best solutions and compare them. The key figure defined as the function to be minimized was finally the investment cost during the lifetime of the installation normalized to the same energy consumption of the house, named as the specific cost of energy (SCE). Therefore, the investment, and thus the economic profitability is not only affected by the defined costs of the different components, but also by the assumed economic figures. Their large associated uncertainty must be kept in mind as they can widely impact on the profitability, therefore if more time was available, a parametric study, regarding these values, could have been done. In addition, despite the SCE is a very objective key figure, other parameters such as the CO₂ reduction or recycling cost could have been included in the calculation in order to prioritize the most environmentally friendly solutions.

Another assumption which increases the uncertainty of the results for the PHPS design is the stand-by heat losses modelling, as they have been defined dependent on the square root of the volume which might not be the best approach for this PHPS. Given heat losses hinder the feasibility of the storage, as concluded in the section 3.2, the heat losses model should be improved in the future in order to increase the accuracy of the model. A possible solution could be selecting a fixed height to radius ratio which minimizes the area to volume ratio, hence, the heat losses to energy stored is minimized. This change will access a better understanding of this parameter on the performance of the PHPS.

The PVT generation data is calculated from simplified model of a single collector whose electricity and heat production has been scaled up accordingly. Hence, this model is another part which limits the accuracy of the system when scaling from a single module to a larger installation, not only in the electrical part, but also in the thermal part.

Moreover, the model of the LTES and the MTES is also another critical piece in the design since the heat flows inside the tanks cannot be modelled easily. However, designing these tanks in a proper way is out of the scope of this thesis work. Other assumptions such as the charging and discharging losses of the hot water tanks have been set to zero, which should be kept in mind.

As seen in the results, the PV installation size is normally very large for a residential house installation in relation to the limited roof space. Therefore, it should have been limited by the model in order to avoid reaching unreasonable results for a residential house.

It must be kept in mind that despite all the assumptions and simplifications in the model design, this project aimed to have a general idea of what are the challenges of this PHPS technology.

4 Conclusions and future work

In this study, a system with a PV installation and a PHPS to supply the heat and electricity demand of a residential house has been modelled. This PHPS technology is a potential low cost and highly efficient electrical storage if the heat losses are reused and could be an alternative solution to the very well settled storage, the Li-ion. In order to understand better the potential feasibility of this PHPS, it has been compared to the Li-ion battery. However, given its immaturity, the aims of this study are to understand which parameters would have more impact on the economic feasibility. To do so, a parametric study has been done around different variables and this project has assisted in determining how large these impacts are.

From the first results it has been concluded that the installation with the THP used to supply the cooling resulted in too high SCE due to the low COP and large amount of electricity needed in order to reach higher water temperatures than in the EHP scenarios. Maybe in a building with heat waste at 80 °C, this could be an option to be studied. It can also be concluded from these results that the Li-ion with a PVT installation is a good combination in order to cover part of the heating demand with the PVT generation and covering the rest to reach a higher temperature with electricity from the grid, PV or the Li-ion. When there is PVT, the advantage of the PHPS due to the heat waste produced, is counteracted by the PVT production, leading to be the cheapest solution. However, the PVT generation data might be too optimistic since a model of a single collector has been used and scaled up to reach the desired power and maybe with a more accurate mode, the results might differ from the ones in section 3.1. Regardless, a new parametric study should be done in order to check how the cost would impact on the optimum sizes and if there is any scenario in which the PHPS might be more feasible than the Li-ion with the PVT.

For the scenarios with THP, the optimized capacity of the storage is not used efficiently since the SOC is very high during the summer, whilst for the rest of the scenarios, the PHPS is designed more compact.

For the base case (the most realistic scenario), the PHPS size is optimized to zero if the assumed costs are relatively high and the H2P efficiency is lower than 50%, meaning that it is not feasible. However, it is expected that the H2P cost will reach 300 €/kWh, allowing a reduction of the H2P efficiency required in order to reach feasibility.

It has been proved that for all the simulate cases in the parametric study, the H2P efficiency does not impact on the profitability for values over 30-40 % which shows that it is important to reach this efficiency, and other characteristics should be given more attention than this parameter. From the literature it was seen that the TPV technology could potentially reach these H2P efficiencies up to 40 % which value will directly depend inevitably on the cost per power capacity. Therefore, it is clearly seen how important it is for the PHPS to increase the H2P efficiency and reduce its cost, but also to reduce the heat losses for small systems to reduce the dependence on the H2P efficiency. In other words, a trade-off between the heat losses, directly dependent on the insulation quality and its cost must be found for smaller systems, although it seems that in larger systems, the energy cost must be reduced independently of the heat losses.

The PHPS has the possibility of designing both maximum output and input power independently on each other, allowing selecting the most appropriate sizes for each application and load, instead of depending on a fixed maximum power as in the Li-ion case. In addition, despite the expected reduction of the current cost per power capacity of the Li-ion, the room for improvement with respect to this cost is much smaller than for the PHPS. However, it must be mentioned that due to the low PV self-consumption of the Li-ion case, the excess of electricity could be exported to the grid and it could benefit. As opposed to the Li-ion, the PHPS PV self-consumption for low H2P efficiencies is very high but the heat losses in the system are also high, meaning that the Li-ion can benefit from selling to the

grid, whilst the PHPS has heat losses, either from the thermal stand-by losses or from the heat that cannot be used from the H2P unit, cannot be reused. On the contrary, in case of increasing the heating demand compared to the electricity demand, the PHPS could increase the efficiency as the heat losses in the H2P could be better used.

All the results presented are based on a given residential load for a particular location. Any variation over this assumption, such as increasing the heating load, would have an impact on the final results. Hence, further investigation on the impact of the load should be done. In addition, this optimization model could be applied in future work to the industrial or the tertiary sector, whose loads are larger and, as concluded in the project, this benefits the PHPS over the Li-ion. On the author's opinion, systems with very large low temperature heating demand could benefit from implementing a PHPS system.

Other parameter studies regarding the cost of the energy imported from the grid or the location should be done in the future in order to see the impact of the climate, not only in varying the PV generation, but also the load.

Other future improvements to the model could be including decision-making and data prediction models instead of real time updating values. Letting the system decide whether to store electricity or consuming it based on PV generation or the fluctuating exported, and imported energy cost of the grid would introduce an advantage.

Very different scenarios such as including a boiler in order to produce heat could have been analysed but given that the aim of the system was to completely electrify the system, it was decided not to simulate it. In addition, a reversible EHP could have been installed in order to produce heat or even include a thermal collector installation performing at higher temperatures than the PV, however, this could be implemented in future improvements in the model. This is why this tool has a great importance as several scenarios can be optimized in order to calculate not only the components' sizes, but also the economic performances to compare different cases.

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Appendices

Appendix A Heating cooling and electricity loads

The heating, split into SH and DHW are shown in the Figure A.1 and Figure A.2 below. The SH figure shows the demand for the whole year, which is almost zero during the summer. The DHW is shown for a couple of days as it is constant during the year.

Figure A.1. SH demand during the whole year.

Figure A.2. DHW demand for a couple of days.

In the Figure A.3, the cooling demand is shown, where it is clearly seen the seasonal dependence. The electricity demand, which is constant during the year varying hourly, is shown in the Figure A.4. A combination of both the electricity and the electrical cooling demand is shown in the Figure A.5.

Figure A.3. Cooling demand for the whole year.

Figure A.4. Electrical power demand for a couple of days.

Figure A.5. Electrical demand including chiller demand during a year.

Appendix B Model decision tree

Appendix C System control

